

**GENDER FEATURES OF FORMS OF ADDRESS: A CONTRASTIVE
ANALYSIS ENGLISH AND UZBEK LITERARY EXAMPLES**

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Annotation: This article explores the gender-specific features of address terms in Uzbek and English languages through a contrastive analysis of literary works: “Ufq” by Said Ahmad and “Death on the Nile” by Agatha Christie. While both languages share certain similarities in the use of pronominal form of address, significant differences exist in nominal forms of address, particularly in their expression of gender distinctions.

Keywords: forms of address, gender linguistics, kinship terms, pronominal forms of address, patronymic names

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуются гендерно-специфические особенности форм обращения в узбекском и английском языках через контрастный анализ литературных произведений: “Уфк” Саида Ахмада и “Убийство в Ниле” Агаты Кристи. Хотя оба языка имеют определенные сходства в использовании местоименных форм обращения, существует значительная разница в номинативных формах обращения, особенно в их выражении гендерных различий.

Ключевые слова: формы обращения, гендерная лингвистика, термины родства, местоименные формы обращения, отчества.

Zusammenfassung: Dieser Artikel untersucht die geschlechtsspezifischen Merkmale der Anredeformen in den usbekischen und englischen Sprachen durch eine kontrastive Analyse literarischer Werke: “Ufq” von Said Ahmad und “Death on the Nile” von Agatha Christie. Während beide Sprachen gewisse Ähnlichkeiten in der Verwendung pronominaler Anredeformen aufweisen, bestehen signifikante Unterschiede in den nominalen Anredeformen, insbesondere in der Darstellung geschlechtsspezifischer Unterscheidungen.

Schlüsselwörter: Anredeformen, geschlechterlinguistik, Verwandtschaftsbezeichnungen, pronominale Anredeformen, patronymen.

According to Friederike Braun [1;28] in most languages forms of address concentrate on two-word classes:

1. **Pronominal forms of address** (Pronouns that are used as terms of address)
2. **Nominal forms of address** (Names, kinship terms, and descriptive or occupational labels)

Among these 2 categories of address terms only nominal forms of address indicates gender. Analysis of literary works: "Ufq" by Said Ahmad and "Death on the Nile" by Agatha Christie shows that following address terms are marked as gender specific:

Gender characteristics in first-name usage as an address in the Uzbek and English examples. In both Uzbek and English, first names are commonly used as forms of address to establish familiarity or to indicate social affiliations. *Gulnoza, Nigora, Mohira, Dilafruz,* and *Jannat* are typical girl names in Uzbek culture, whereas *Akbar, Umid, Tursunboy, Aziz,* and *Ikrom* are typical male names. [5] For example, in Uzbek -*Jannat, Jannat, senga nima bo'ldi? Jannat ingradi. Ikrom ariqdan hovuchida suv olib betiga sochdi. Jannat ko'zini ochdi.* [2;7] - *Bolaginamga so'yib bering. Yesin. Tursunboy, bolaginam, qanisan* [2:7] In English, -*How beastly you are, Joanna!* [3;13] 3. *I am not counting my chickens before they are hatched, Simon.* [3;21]

Gender characteristics in last-name usage as an address in the Uzbek English examples. Last names serve as formal means of address in both Uzbek and English, but they differ significantly in terms of gender. In Uzbek, surnames are often gender-specific, with suffixes like "-ov/-ev" for males and "-ova/-eva" for females, making it easy to determine the gender of the addressee [4]. For instance: "- *O'rtoq Yusupov, kanal ishlari terim sur'atiga ta'sir ko'rsatmasligi kerak*" and [2;128] In contrast, English last names are typically gender-neutral, and gender is indicated through honorifics such as "Mr.", "Miss", "Mrs.", or "Ms." For example: "Well, you see, *Mr. Doyle, to begin with she is not a man*" [3; 72], "Well, *Miss Bowers, so you are off to Europe? – Why, yes, Mrs. Robson*" [3;33], and "There is only one woman in the world I've got a real respect and admiration for. And I think, *Mrs. Allerton, you know very well who that woman is*" [3;32]. While Uzbek surnames reflect gender inherently, English relies on contextual and honorific cues.

Using first name + last name as an address form, a comparative analysis of gender characteristics in Uzbek and English. In the given examples, gender can be seen differently in English and Uzbek languages. In English, the first name often shows gender, as seen in "- *Linnet Ridgeway, can you look me in the face and tell me of any one occasion on which you've failed to do exactly as you wanted?*" [3;23], where Linnet is a distinctly female name. Similarly, in "- *Oh, no, Colonel Race, of course not. Miss Van Schuyler did.* [3;198], the name Colonel is apparently male name. However, in Uzbek, both the first name and last name contribute to gender

identification. For example, “- **Georgiy Zelma**, “*Ogonyok*” *jurnalining maxsus fotomuxbiriman. Ijzat bersangiz, men yosh polvon Azizxon Ummataliyevga bir-ikkita savol bersam.*” [2;213] clearly refers to a male individual, as Georgiy is a male first name. This difference demonstrates how Uzbek incorporates both first and last names for gender differentiation, while English mostly uses first names and honorific titles.

Gender Distinctions in First Name + Patronymic Usage within Uzbek and English Examples. Patronymic names are a polite and formal way to address someone in Uzbek as in this example, “-*Gunohidan o’ting, Usmon Yusupovich.*” [2; 80] English does not use patronymics to indicate gender in address, although Uzbek does.

Gender Features in Nickname Usage in Uzbek and English. In both contrasted languages nicknames reveal gender when used as address terms. For example, in Uzbek “*Lutfi, sen ketaver, men hozir boraman. Istalovoydan menga ham joy olib tur, orqangdan yetib boraman.*” [2; 124]. In English, “*We will see it together, Jackie... together. Won’t it be marvelous?*” [3;21].

Gender features in kinship terms as forms of address, within the examples of Uzbek and English. In both languages’ kinship terms are used to address family members and close relatives and most of them mark gender. As it can be seen in the following examples: “- *Ummatali amaki, tez uyga borarkansiz.*” [2;15] or in English, “*Why of course, Uncle Andrew. Linnet at once became businesslike. My marriage has made a difference, of course.*” [3;96]. Most of the kinship terms in Uzbek language are used to address strangers while the English mostly prefers using gender markers/honorifics to address people.

Occupational titles as forms of address reflecting gender. Occupational titles are used as forms of address in both Uzbek and English, and they frequently reflect gender differences. The gender of the person being addressed is made evident in Uzbek by gendered forms such as “*kotib*” (male secretary) and “*kotiba*” (female secretary), or “*shoir*” (male poet) and “*shoira*” (female poet). Similarly, gender-specific professional terminology like “*actor*” and “*actress*”, or “*waiter*” (male) and “*waitress*” (female), are used in English. These titles express the addressee's gender identification in addition to their job.

In conclusion, the study showed how crucial address phrases are to communication. In particular, gendered forms of address draw attention to the ways in which language encodes expectations and social relationships.

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"ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIK VA TARJIMASHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI"
mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

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